

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AL SALHI****FIRST NAME: ZAINAB****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

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Actual information below:

The author followed the American rules of grammar, usage, and syntax

I used Turabian/Chicago-style references in the text

I did not use Zotero to insert references

I used Grammarly Premium

Grammarly Premium plagiarism rate: 3%

Software used: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List my critical concepts with the page number in the text:

1. Use of italics in academic texts (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 47)
2. Use of quotation marks in academic texts (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 47-48)
3. Difference between using italics and quotation marks (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 47-48)
4. Impact on text clarity (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 47)
5. Common mistakes in using italics and quotation marks (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 47-48)
6. Using italics for emphasis on special or new terms (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 47)

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THE ROLE OF ITALICS AND QUOTATION MARKS IN ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

When we write in the academic field, our ideas must be clear and well-organized so readers can easily understand what we are trying to say. Italics and quotation marks are two essential tools to achieve this goal. We usually use italics to indicate the titles of long books and journals and highlight scientific names and foreign words. On the other hand, we use quotation marks mainly for the titles of articles and chapters and also to clarify direct speech. If we understand how to use these tools correctly, we can write academic texts that are organized and easy to read. This paper will discuss the use of italics and quotation marks, explain their differences, examine their effect on text clarity, and highlight some common mistakes and ways to avoid them (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 45-52).

2) USE OF ITALICS IN ACADEMIC TEXTS

Using italics in academic writing greatly helps distinguish some essential parts. We usually use it to indicate the titles of books, magazines, and works of art and when mentioning scientific names and foreign terms. Using italics regularly makes it easier for the reader to recognize these elements and navigate between parts of the text quickly (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 45-48). Italics give the text a different visual appearance, making it more attractive.

3) USE OF QUOTATION MARKS IN ACADEMIC TEXTS

In academic writing, we commonly use quotation marks to indicate the titles of articles or short chapters and clarify direct speech. Correctly using quotation marks helps us organize the text more clearly and distinguish between what is quoted and our text when the text reflects the thoughts of the mind.

The real power is revealed in "suggestion," where the meaning is not presented as it is but leaves room for contemplation, analysis, and exploration of the depths.

Ideas can sometimes be ambiguous, waiting for readers to discover their meaning through careful thinking and contrasting feelings.

Quotation marks are not used to clarify the quoted words; instead, they are a clever tool that clarifies the depth of the idea. When the writer uses quotation marks, he usually wants the reader to stop for a moment to think and analyze, but in an indirect way. Sometimes, the writer also intends to add a kind of intelligence or sarcasm so that the reader thinks about the subject from different angles. We can say that the writer deliberately makes the reader need to think more and more.

In this way, facts are not presented ready-made, but rather, the reader can create his vision so that ideas are freely intertwined in his mind.

4) DIFFERENCE BETWEEN USING ITALICS AND QUOTATION MARKS

Both italics and quotation marks have different functions. Italics are used for precise and specialized concepts and words to clarify long works. Writers use quotation marks to quote someone's speech directly and to highlight written works or short texts, such as dialogue excerpts. Also, we as academic writers must know precisely when to use these tools and how to use them because they will help convey the message and ideas to the reader quickly and without confusion or ambiguity (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 65-68). The incorrect use of italics and quotation marks makes the text confusing for the reader because he will feel that the text is unclear because instead of these tools helping him

understand the idea, on the contrary, he will feel lost and hesitant because the text with these errors will be weakened and the writer will not be able to convey the message effectively and correctly (WeAreDrew Editorial Team 2024).

5) IMPACT ON TEXT CLARITY

All research and studies have concluded that the correct use of italics and quotation marks helps the reader interact with the text. For example, using italics to highlight titles and terms gives the text a distinctive character for the reader. Even the quotation mark, in its role in separating the transferred or borrowed information from the writer's information, also contributes to the smoothness and organization of the text, which contributes to the reader's better understanding. Such things help raise the level of professionalism in writing and give quality to the work (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 45-52). Also, paying attention to these details makes the reader feel the text's coherence, the ideas it contains, and the organization.

6) COMMON MISTAKES IN USING ITALICS AND QUOTATION MARKS

Most people make mistakes when using italics; for example, when they use it to distinguish titles, they sometimes leave some titles unformatted. They also sometimes need to learn to use quotation marks for emphasis or to highlight a phrase, but this is a mistake; people use quotation marks to quote someone literally or to specify the titles of articles or stories. Such mistakes need to be clarified for the reader and also reduce the quality of academic work.

7) USING ITALICS FOR EMPHASIS ON SPECIAL OR NEW TERMS

We can use italics to highlight an idea or a term we use. This makes it easy for readers to recognize the idea, so it is expected to attract the reader's attention. We can use this method if we want to explain a new concept. The concept will be visually attractive and help the reader follow the ideas. Therefore, italics are a way to attract the reader's attention and are not just a way to highlight words.

8) CORRECT USE OF QUOTATION MARKS FOR EXPRESSING EXCEPTIONS OR IRONY

Quotation marks are not only used to indicate quoted texts or direct dialogues, but they are also used for complex purposes to indicate exceptions, sarcasm, or hint at indirect

meanings without explaining in detail, and the same thing in the case of sarcasm by adding a sense of sarcasm or humor to the text, in this way, we can add complexity to the text to make the reader attentive and make him interact with every word instead of comprehending the text superficially, in this case, if we use quotation marks in the wrong place it will cause confusion for the reader, and he may misunderstand the words. However, we use quotation marks for the proper purpose. In that case, we can create a connection between the writer and the reader, and the reader will be able to notice the level of the writer's experience and interact with him positively.

Using quotation marks effectively conveys ideas accurately. The book does not need to express itself directly; on the contrary, adopting this method makes the reader try to understand the meaning, analyze, and see the idea from all sides instead of taking it superficially. Also, the quotation mark attracts the reader's attention when he focuses on borrowed information, quoted ideas, or humorous critical ideas. This helps the reader focus on the text and encourages the m to enjoyreading.

9) CONCLUSION

The use of italics and quotation marks is essential in academic writing. It helps us understand and distinguish the text's elements and helps readers follow ideas smoothly.

Italics distinguish titles, terms, and sources, making it easier for the reader to understand the ideas and their sequence.

Quotation marks are also essential to distinguish the words quoted. This approach gives the text more credibility and makes the reader trust the presented content.

These tools give an impression of the writer's professionalism and knowledge of all academic writing skills.

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